

ٹرانس جینڈر اور تبدیلی جنس کا شرعی حکم

**TRANSGENDER IDENTITY AND THE SHARIAH
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ABSTRACT

Transgender individuals face numerous challenges in society, including discrimination and stigma. In many religious communities, there is also debate and disagreement over the acceptability of gender transition. This paper explores the religious perspective on transgender individuals and gender transition, specifically in the Islamic context. Through a review of Islamic texts, the opinions of Islamic scholars, and contemporary discussions on the topic, this paper seeks to provide a comprehensive understanding of the religious rulings and ethical considerations surrounding gender transition. The key findings of this paper suggest that while some scholars view gender transition as impermissible, others argue that it can be permissible under certain conditions. Ultimately, this paper highlights the need for greater inclusivity and understanding of transgender individuals within religious communities.

Keywords: Transgender, Gender Transition, Islamic Context, Religious Rulings.

کلیدی الفاظ: ٹرانس جینڈر، تبدیلی جنس، شرعی حکم، دینی احکامات۔

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